

Psychological Influences of Artificial Intelligence Integration in Curriculum Restructuring among Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

Gital Ahmed Abdullahi

Federal University of Education, Zaria.

gitalahmedabdullahi@gmail.com

07067792405

The psychological influences in the curriculum restructuring in tertiary institutions and the relevance of integrating artificial intelligence into the curriculum restructuring for sustainable development in Nigeria are very significant. This study assessed the psychological influences of artificial intelligence integration in curriculum restructuring among tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper explored relevant literature and discussed psychological influences in the restructuring of the curriculum in tertiary institutions. The arguments for integrating artificial intelligence into the tertiary education curriculum in Nigeria for sustainable education development are also discussed in the work. The paper concluded that psychological principles, foundations, and theories, among others, are highly needed in curriculum restructuring. More so, the integration of ICT in the curriculum restructuring is valuable for sustainable education development in Nigeria. The paper recommended, among others, the provision of funds to support the restructuring of inclusive curriculum, psychological consideration, and ICT integration to support digitalising the education system and attain sustainable education development in Nigeria.

Keywords:
Psychological Influences, Artificial Intelligence, Integration, Curriculum, Restructuring, Tertiary Institutions

Introduction

Education remains a veritable mechanism for sustainable national development. Thus, sustainable education development in all tertiary institutions in Nigeria becomes imperative in the recent modern society. UNESCO (2021) perceived education for sustainable development as a response to the urgent and dramatic challenges the planet faces. Sustainable educational development targets learners of all ages and aims to equip them with knowledge, skills, values, and agency to address interconnected global challenges, including climate change, loss of biodiversity, unsustainable use of resources, and inequality. Sustainable education development is a lifelong learning process that will empower students, irrespective of background, to make informed decisions and

take an individual and collective approach to change society and care for the environment (UNESCO, 2021). Sustaining education development can promote the cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural dimensions of learning and improve learning materials, content, and outcomes, as well as pedagogy and the learning environment as a whole.

Quality sustainability of education development is anchored on a well-structured and functional curriculum. Wiles (2005) regarded curriculum as a set of values that is activated through a development process and culminates in classroom experiences for students. The curriculum is a total of all the experiences that students undergo within the guidance of the school which includes educational objectives, learning experiences,

and methods of evaluation in the curriculum-building process (Syomwene et al, 2013). Curriculum connotes collaborations among the community, the state, and educational professionals regarding the educational interactions that learners should go through during a specific stage in life, including why they are gaining knowledge, what to acquire when to learn, how to perceive learning, and with whom to trust learning (Pastory, 2016). The curriculum reflects the society and culture of a country, hence the society desires that the habits, ideas, attitudes, and skills embedded in the culture should be imparted to the students (Satraddhar, 2021). In a broader perspective, the curriculum is both planned and unplanned learning experiences to which learners are introduced within and outside the classroom setting for personal and societal growth, as outlined in a guided policy to represent how the policy will be implemented through a plan of action (Dellosa, 2022).

To achieve a functionally relevant curriculum for sustainable development in modern society, there is a need for constant, effective restructuring. According to Dellosa (2022), restructuring curriculum is the systematic rebuilding of an educational process to provide effective teaching and learning for learners of all ethnicities, genders, economic backgrounds, and other student attributes. Curriculum restructuring will focus on the academic foundations, learning contents, and their sequential procedures related to learning opportunities, characteristics of learning institutions, teaching methodologies, sources/materials for learning and teaching, assessment methods, and the resource person's educational background (Dellosa, 2022; Pastory, 2016; Satradhar, 2021). The flexible restructuring will enable sufficient acquisition of knowledge and transformation of learners'

perspectives, behaviours, awareness, and inspiration. Restructuring the curriculum will be possible if the changes consider students, teachers, and administrators and then focus on their awareness and experiences on the issues of past and present educational systems to meet the learning demands of several learners.

The psychological influences in the curriculum restructuring in all tertiary institutions are paramount since the students are the key beneficiaries. This is because psychology plays a vital role in the teaching-learning process. According to Cherry (2022), educational psychology is the study of how people learn, including teaching methods, instructional processes, and individual differences in learning. The psychological foundation in curriculum restructuring is based on individual differences, where every student has a unique personality and differences in nature. As such, students cannot be treated the same during the teaching and learning process. Therefore, the curriculum restructuring should be designed to support the capacity and potential of all students. Psychology lays a foundation in the selection of methods of teaching, the selection of content of subjects, and the methods and theories of learning, as well as the overall development of the students by inculcating the norms of society. Psychology helps to explore the cognitive, behavioural, emotional, and social influences on the learning process.

To make curriculum restructuring all-encompassing and effective, educational psychologists recommended the inclusion of educational technology (looking at how different types of technology can help students learn); instructional design (designing effective learning materials); special education (helping students who may need specialized instruction); and organizational learning (studying how people learn in

organizational settings, such as workplaces) among many (Cherry, 2022). In Nigeria, it seems that the old curriculum is not keying into promoting educational technology, digital instructional design, organized online instruction, and specialized instruction for special needs students in tertiary institutions. Udofia (2021) posits that the old curriculum is reviewed in line with the demand for international best practices in education, evolving multinational agreements in education, new National policies, changing social order, and the globally acceptable standards in education especially as it concerned child's right to free education and poverty eradication as contained in the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the National Economic Empowerment Development Strategy and the vision 20-20-20, as well as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In addition, the old curriculum insufficiently addressed the challenges associated with the paradigm shift in science, technology, and other emerging digital issues. Students who are the product of such a curriculum were ill-prepared to face the challenges of the world of work as they lacked basic life-long skills, functional literacy and numeracy skills, and information and communication skills, among many (Federal Ministry of Education, 2008). This has resulted in serious cases of unemployment, inadequate skillful manpower to manage the industrial revolution for sustainable national development, and a critical mass of graduates that are not job initiators but are weak and too subsistent to keep pace with the demand of international competitiveness (Karseth, 2014). There is no doubt that the high level of insecurity in Nigeria may be connected to the flaws of the curriculum and the inability to

restructure it to be attuned to the current trend of fast technological changes.

Nevertheless, integrating artificial intelligence into the tertiary education curricula can provide a high level of sustainable education development in Nigeria. Artificial intelligence is the type of technology designed in the form of tools, equipment, and application support that helps in the collection, storage, retrieval, use, transmission, manipulation, and dissemination of information as accurately and efficiently as possible (Monichatterjee, 2021; Soeiono, 2021). AI was invented to enrich the knowledge and develop communication, decision-making as well as problem-solving ability of the beneficiaries. Integrating ICT into the curriculum will help in transitioning from a traditional mode of learning to interactive learning, thereby making the students active and participating in the teaching-learning process. Students will become self-reliant and self-directed in the acquisition and application of knowledge and skills. It will, among many benefits, create a more interactive and engaging learning environment for both teachers and students.

It has been observed that much literature has been written about AI and education, curriculum restructuring, both in Nigeria and outside, but the psychological influences in the curriculum restructuring in tertiary institutions and the relevance of integrating ICT into the curriculum restructuring for sustainable development in Nigeria are not being thoroughly explored. This study assessed the psychological influences of curriculum restructuring in tertiary education and the significance of integrating ICT into the restructuring process for sustainable development.

Psychological Influences in Curriculum Restructuring

The curriculum structure is like the skeleton of a body. It is strong and gives balance, direction, and support to the activities in the body. Restructuring the curriculum in tertiary institutions will serve as the skeleton of education. Curriculum restructuring considers relevant themes and arranging them, the agreement over the theoretical educational framework, the goals, and content (Oliver et al. 2007). According to Dellosa (2022) curriculum restructuring is the transformation of educational schemes, such as their design, objectives, and subject matter that pertains to the connections between syllabi designers, syllabi evaluators (examination organizations), syllabi practitioners (teachers), syllabi clients (students), syllabi implementation evaluators (school supervisors), graduate consumers (employers), and contributing education stakeholders (parents and community members). In the past, the curriculum was developed in traditional ways without keeping in view the psychological implications of the development of the curriculum. However, psychology is the core and foundation elements of all the learning processes; curriculum development, child's mental development, teaching methods, learning theories, administration of education system and planning, character building of the students, the attitude of students and teacher, the society, and the use of different technologies (Satraddhar, 2021). Psychology helps in all fields of education, hence the need for the utilization of such influences. The significance of psychology goes beyond increasing knowledge, it is applied in a practical classroom situation as well as in the curriculum development process by defining

teaching methods and approaching the needs of the learners.

In tertiary education, students are from different ethnoreligious backgrounds, ages, and gender. Educational psychology studies learners and learning contexts both within and beyond traditional classrooms and evaluate ways in which factors such as age, culture, gender, and physical and social environments influence human learning (Psychology.org Staff, 2022). Psychology will leverage educational theory and practice, and human development to understand the emotional, cognitive, and social aspects of human learning. Concepts from educational psychology can be embedded in the curriculum to help educators understand and address the ways rapidly changing technologies either help or destroy students' learning. In addition, psychology provides bases for collaboration among the stakeholders (parents, students, and teachers) to improve a child's learning outcomes. Consequently, curriculum reform should have direct and clear objectives that are easily understood by the specific population and society as a whole (Cohen, 2025; Kotter & Cohen, 2022). The restructuring of the curriculum should be based on the psychological paradigms which include behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism, humanism, and socio-cultural.

Integrating AI Into Tertiary Education Curriculum

Restructuring and achieving the objectives of tertiary education curricula in the fast-changing technological world will be easy with the incorporation of AI. According to Monichatterjee (2021), AI is the type of technology in the shape of tools, equipment, and application support, that helps in the collection, storage, retrieval, use,

transmission, manipulation, and dissemination of information as accurately and efficiently as possible. AI include hardware devices connected to computers, and software applications, interactive digital content, internet, and other satellite communication devices, radio and television services, web-based content repositories, interactive forums, learning management systems, and management information systems among many others. All these elements and platforms are needed for the effective implementation of the curriculum in tertiary institutions and the realization of broad and specific educational goals.

When importance is given to AI, the curriculum development process set for the transfer of learning and future learning will be actualized. The methods of teaching will be a guided discovery that will strengthen the relationships among the student learning outcomes, subject matter, and the environment. The interest and motivation level of the students will be generated using AI. Students can engage in meaningful conversation which helps the students to generate new ideas, make new interpretations and raise new questions. The use of AI will enable students to gain in-depth knowledge about a topic and help them apply different ideas, processes, theories, and models. The embedding of AI will not only benefit the students but the teachers and the school management as well. Monichatterjee (2021) and Soeiono (2021) shared similar arguments for the use of AI in education. Some of these arguments are summarized, thus:

1. AI can bring the existing educational system in alignment with the knowledge-based, information-rich society by providing services of sophisticated tools, techniques, and methods at its disposal.

2. Use of AI can bring about a paradigm shift in traditional views and methods of the teaching-learning process. Example: changes the role of teachers from a mere knowledge transmitter to that of a learning facilitator, knowledge guide or navigator and an active co-learner along with students; enables students to become more responsible about their learning as they seek out relevant information and knowledge through their efforts, synthesize and share their knowledge with others; makes students realize their educational potentials; AI helps students to think critically and creatively and to reflect on their learning process. Students can even set their individual goals for the growth and development of their potential.

3. AI prepares teachers to meet the challenges of the teaching-learning task of the modern age. It helps teachers in the proper execution of their multi-dimensional responsibilities in various areas of education.

4. AI can be beneficial not only to teachers for their education and training but also to use it creatively for accelerating the educational growth of their students.

From all indications, AI will be useful for a teacher in professional development (learning different skills) and participate in various in-service training programs and workshops which are essential for his professional development. AI will increase the teacher's domain of knowledge through the help of e-journals, e-magazines, and e-library. AI will help a teacher to learn innovative methods of teaching and to guide his students about the learning materials available on the internet, e-books, e-journals, e-magazines, and social sites. It will also assist the teacher in framing the curriculum that will lead to achieving the aims and objectives of the subject of teaching. In addition, with AI, students can study through online resources,

meet teachers online and get required knowledge about the subject, as well as have no limit of time and place for study, especially at this time that academic activities in tertiary institutions in Nigeria are marred by handful of crises.

Conclusion

From the discussion in this paper, it can be concluded that the impact of psychological content on the foundations of curriculum restructuring in tertiary education in Nigeria is very significant and remains a life-long influence. The application of scope, principles, concepts, theories, and processes of psychology in the construction, restructuring, and implementation of the curriculum in tertiary education in Nigeria is vital considering individual differences. The role of psychology in the development of the curriculum is vast and each day it is becoming increasingly more meaningful and demanded. In this regard, there is a need for different AI platforms and facilities through which the teaching-learning process will become easier. These facilities have helped teachers and students to communicate with each other and get knowledge of a particular subject. Teachers are expected to learn different AI platforms and use them for teaching, while the students use them for the learning process. Thus, AI tools are helpful in these crises and pandemic situations. There should be a functional mechanism and sufficient funding by the government and private individuals to support curriculum restructuring. This will help to facilitate the completion of an inclusive and comprehensive curriculum that accommodates the psychological differences of active stakeholders. The curriculum developers should not neglect the amount of time, AI resources, and energy required to bring about the restructuring. For example, the

normal workload of the facilitators (teachers) and consumers (students) should be balanced accordingly, and managerial and secretarial support should be provided. The process of curricular restructuring should often consider teachers with a richer didactic armamentarium. Teachers have to adapt the psychological approaches to teaching methods, learning needs, and child development when the curriculum in tertiary institutions is restructured. This adaptation calls for support in the form of educational training in AI and professional development. In restructuring a curriculum, there is a need to create amongst teachers a self-determined need for pedagogic education and training in AI that will be much more effective. Thus, the higher authorities should persuade all staff in tertiary institutions in Nigeria to enroll. The key objective of a new and innovative curriculum should give tertiary education an impression of digitalizing the education system. This can be possible through negotiations over budgets, new structures, and new AI equipment among others.

References

- Cherry, K. (2022). *What is psychology of education?* Retrieved 2/11/2022 from <https://www.verywellmind.com/What-Is-Educational-Psychology?> (verywellmind.com)
- Cohen, D.S. (2025). *The heart of change field guide*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Dellosa, R.N. (2022). *Significance of restructuring curriculum*. Depedbataan.com publication. Retrieved 3/11/2022 from https://old.depedbataan.com/resources/4/significance_of_restructuring_curriculum.pdf

- Federal Ministry of Education (2008). *Teacher handbook for the 9-year basic education curriculum, basic science for junior secondary school Abuja*. Abuja Nigeria: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), Abuja
- Karseth, K. (2014). Curriculum restructuring in higher education after the bologna process: a new pedagogic regime? *Revista Española de Educación Comparada*, 12 (2006), 255-284
- Kotter, J.P., & Cohen, D.S. (2022). *The heart of change*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Monichatterjee, D. (2021). *Important of ICT in education and teaching learning process*. Retrieved 4/11/2022 from <https://monichatterjee.medium.com/important-of>
- Oliver, R., Kersten, H., Vinkka-Puhakka, H., Alpasan, G., Bearn, D., Cema, I., Delap, E., Dummer, P. et al... (2007). Curriculum structure: principles and strategy. *European Journal of Dental Education*, 12(1), 74-84
- Oliver, R., Kersten, H., Vinkka-Puhakka, H., Alpasan, G., Bearn, D., Cema, I., Delap, E., Dummer, P. et al... (2007).
- Psychology.org Staff (2022). *Introduction to educational psychology theory*. Retrieved 2/11/2022 from <https://www.psychology.org/resources/educational-psychology-theories/>
- Satradhar, D. (2021). *Psychological foundation of curriculum*. Retrieved 3/11/2022 from <https://yoursmartclass.com/psychological-foundation-of-curriculum/>
- Soeiono, J.G. (2021). *The importance of the integration of ICT in education*. Retrieved 4/11/2022 from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351633588>
- Syomwene, A., Kitainge, K., & Mwaka, M. (2013). Psychological influences in the curriculum decision making process. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(8), 173-180
- Udofia, N.A. (2021). The new educational curriculum in Nigeria. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies in Education*, 1(1), 1-20
- UNESCO (2021). *Education for sustainable development*. Retrieved 3/11/2022 from <https://en.unesco.org/partnerships/partnering/education-sustainable-development>
- Wiles, J., (2005). *Curriculum essentials: A resource for educators (2nd Ed.)*. Boston: Pearson Education Inc